

A HARMONIOUS PERSONALITY IS THE PRODUCT OF A STRONG FAMILY.

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The dwelling where a person grows up is a family. The stability of the family, the upbringing of a healthy and harmonious generation — determines the level of development of the state and society. As you know, the family is the first and foremost link of society. Society consists of these connections. If there are more than 7 billion inhabitants on earth, each of them has its own character, one person differs from another in some aspect, which means that there are no people who exactly repeat each other in the world. It goes without saying that families are not similar to each other, since people are unique.

Family members are united with each other by a common marriage, mutual economic and property, legal, moral, spiritual. The first task of the family is the continuation of its kind, the upbringing of righteous and immaculate children, ensuring the livelihood of family members, and voluntary leisure activities.

Family relations are a relatively independent phenomenon, and no one has the right to interfere in the internal affairs of the family in Hudain. For this reason, the family is considered sacred and inviolable. Family relations are determined by the existing social, economic, ideological and spiritual relations in society, and they continue to change within the framework of influence. These relationships are a living, changing process. Accordingly, each society chooses and forms its own and appropriate type of family. For example, there are certain differences between the Uzbek family of the XII century and the Uzbek family of today. Chapter XIV of our Constitution is called "the family", and the presence of the norm in article 63: "the family is the main link in society and has the right to be protected by society and the state" is an example of attention to the institution of the family at the level of State policy. Therefore, the fact that the family is not only protected by law, but also its development and activities are in the care of the state, differs from the attention of other countries of the world. It should be noted that the role of the family in the formation of civil society is impeccable. After all, civil society consists of perfect people, that is, morally, spiritually, physically, mentally and mentally perfect people. And the family is the most necessary, or rather, the most basic and most important dwelling, which creates the qualities inherent in a perfect person.

The fate and future of the nation depend on the younger generation. Their perfection is based on the fact that we can look into our future with hope. The President expressed the need to educate the same young and harmonious generation in his thoughts that "we will build our future with our own hands." Our leader has repeatedly stressed that not only the family and the state, but also members of society as a whole are responsible for the improvement of the younger generation, the masters of our future.

Today it is no secret that the XXI century, in which we live, is the age of intellectual wealth. It is inevitable that such a society will remain aloof from the path of world development if society does not realize this fact in time, the pursuit of intellectual knowledge, intellectual wealth will not become the meaning of its daily life. Although we set ourselves such a very difficult goal, the role and influence of our women in the realization of such a great gift and the upbringing of a harmonious generation in all possible ways cannot be compared with anything. Only a healthy child is born from a healthy mother. Only wise, enlightened mothers will be able to raise a perfect person.

With a deep understanding of this fact, it is gratifying that our programs and activities aimed at strengthening women's health in our country, protecting the family, motherhood and childhood, educating the younger generation, physically, intellectually and spiritually mature, thoughtfully and carefully developed and consistently implemented in life, are bearing fruit today.

Such attention, in turn, has a positive effect on strengthening the atmosphere of kindness, mutual respect in the life of society, strengthening the family instinct, raising a healthy and harmonious generation.

By healthy generation we all mean, first of all, healthy offspring. In this regard, over the years, a wide range of measures has been developed and implemented on the basis of a program embodying the idea of "a healthy mother is a healthy child".

We know very well that the upbringing of a child worthy of an El-yurt is deeply rooted, first of all, in the bosom of the family, in the conditions of a healthy family climate, the love and respect of parents for each other.

From this it is concluded that we know that a healthy and strong family is, first of all, a priority for the issue of young families in the conditions of new construction, which is in the constant attention of our state and society, our districts. It is necessary to continue comprehensive work on strengthening the family, strengthening care for young families, ensuring their legal and social protection, creating the necessary conditions for building a healthy and strong family.

It is in the bosom of the family that there is no need to talk for a long time about the birth of a child, his growing up as a person and a citizen, in an atmosphere of mutual love, parental care. The concepts of honesty, kindness and kindness, a sense of respect for adults appear, first of all, in the family, it is in this environment that a person's worldview is formed in the spirit of national and universal values.

References:

1. Рахманов Б.У. Инсоннинг руҳий-маънавий ўз-ўзини ташкиллаштиришини фалсафий асослаш // фалсафа доктори (PhD) диссертацияси автореферати, Самарфанд, 2017. –Б. 13
2. BA Kurbanovna. Trends in parliamentary effectiveness in ensuring the development of society. Восточно-европейский научный журнал, 33-36, 2020
3. BA Kurbanovna. Development And Role Of Representative Authority In The Development Of Society, Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching 2, 113-117, 2021
4. JI Baxytovna. Science in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. European journal of business startups and open society 2 (3), 82-85, 2022

- 5.IB Jolibekova. Training of personel in the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the years of Independence. Science and Education in Karakalpakstan 2 (2), 104-108, 2019
- 6.IB Jolibekova. International Relations in the field of education in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.Science and Education in Karakalpakstan 2 (2), 93-99, 2018
- 7.ИБ Жоллыбекова. Вопросы оценки образования в современных условиях. атериалы международной научно-практической конференции 1 (2), 69-71, 2017
- 8.IB Jolibekova. Features of the development of International economic relations Republic of Karakalpakstan at the present stage. I International Conference on Suistanble Development and Economics 1 (1 ..., 2017)
- 9.IB Jolibekova. Peculiarities of development of international economic relations of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Europe Applied Science. Europaiche Fachhochshule 1 (1), 400-402, 2015

